

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	1.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	22
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.4	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	28
D06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.7	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	34
D09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.5	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	30
E06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	2.3	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	46
E08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	1.2	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	24
E09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	2.1	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	42

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				0	14016						14016
				59	14253						14312
				0	15790						15790
				0	15401						15401
		1.8	0.6	12	13182						13194
				14	14287						14301
				0	15196						15196
				0	15030						15030
				12	14159						14171
				0	13074						13074
				0	15977						15977
		2.1	0.8	19	16538						16557
				0	15071						15071
				28	14524						14552
		2.4	1.1	23	16364						16387
		2.3	1	21	16132						16153
				0	13986						13986
		3.3	1.6	29	14608						14637
		1.9	0.7	17	16155						16172
		2.9	1.4	31	17599						17630

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	0	0	7906
	1	1	8179	9007.4	7364.3
	1	1	0	0	5004.2
	1	1	0	0	4719.3
	1	1	8940	10628	8080.9
	1	1	8301	9612.7	7486.8
	1	1	0	0	5304.8
	1	1	0	0	5063.7
	1	1	8861	11500	7968.3
	1	1	0	0	7125.9
	1	1	0	0	5345.5
	1	1	5747	8930.6	5107.4
	1	1	0	0	8320.8
	1	1	8770	10290	7876.3
	1	1	8961	24772	5767.8
	1	1	7191	20531	5582.7
	1	1	0	0	8141.9
	1	1	8591	10104	7611.8
	1	1	6625	21233	5669
	1	1	6231	13099	5474

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68
7906	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7371.1	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5004.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4719.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
8083.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.41	0.79
7488.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5304.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5063.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7971.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7125.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5345.5	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5111.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.68	1.06
8320.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7881	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
5794.5	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.02	1.33
5602.1	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.89	1.22
8141.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7616.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.79	1.93
5685.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.56	0.96
5487.4	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.46	1.72

